

ROSIE

D8.5: Events

Authors: Vana Stavridi, Panagiotis Kavouras

Editors: Costas Charitidis

Project title: Responsible Open Science in Europe

Project acronym: ROSiE

Grant Agreement no.: 101006430

Lead contractor for this deliverable: National Technical University of Athens

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101006430
Project Acronym:	ROSiE
Project Title:	Responsible Open Science in Europe
Title of Deliverable:	Events
Work Package:	8
Due date according to contract:	M24- 28 February 2023
Editor(s):	Costas Charitidis
Contributor(s):	Vana Stavridi, Panagiotis Kavouras
Reviewer(s):	-
Approved by	Rose Bernabe

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1 Introduction

Events (conferences, workshops, public events) constitute the offline channels of communication and dissemination activities promoting the results and various outputs of any research project, further to scientific publications. In the case of ROSiE, dissemination and communication activities, such as events, are in the core of the project's development and progress. Furthermore, due to the project's topic and the synthesis of the consortium, which covers a wide range of principles, the variety of events in which ROSiE can be addressed is wide, giving the opportunity to raise awareness on the project's developments and increase visibility in multiple levels, while interacting with various types of stakeholders.

D8.5: Events contains a list of relevant events in which ROSiE consortium members have participated or plan to participate during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd year of the project (March 2021 -December 2023). These events are not necessarily events organized by ROSiE, but events in which ROSiE will be communicated in any way, whether via a ROSiE-related presentation, a panel discussion or informal discussions, so as to raise awareness on the project. This deliverable will be updated each year by NTUA. The first version **D8.5 Events** was submitted in M3, the second one in M12, and the third one in M24 and an updated version of it will be submitted in M36.

Consortium:

No.	Role	Name	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	ÖSTERREICHISCHE AGENTUR FÜR WISSENSCHAFTLICHE INTEGRITÄT	OeAWI	Austria
3.	Partner	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	EUREC OFFICE GUG	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAINVALTUUSKUNNASTA	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	HAUT CONSEIL DE L'EVALUATION DE LA RECHERCHE ET DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SUPÉRIEUR	HCERES	France
7.	Partner	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
8.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece

9.	Partner	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICAPORTUGUESA	UCP	Portugal
10.	Partner	LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATE	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	TARTU ULIKOOL	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	Norway

No	Event	Dates	Venue	City	Country	Name of attendee/ Entity	Related ROSiE WP	Reason for participation	Title of contribution (if applicable)	Type of contribution (Oral presentation, Poster presentation)	Comments
2021											
MARCH 2021											
1	ENRIO member's corner	24 March 2021	Online event	-	-	Panagiotis Kavouras	WP8	Communicating the initiation of ROSiE	ROSiE: Responsible Open Science in Europe	Oral presentation	An interesting discussion followed the presentation
APRIL 2021											
2	University of Latvia Science Night	30 April 2021	Online event	Riga	Latvia	Signe Mezinska	WP8	Panel discussion on citizen science	Ethical aspects of citizen science	Participation in a panel discussion	Information about the panel discussion where the ROSiE project is mentioned (in Latvian) https://www.biblioteka.lu.lv/lv/parmums/zinas/zina/t/65917/
MAY 2021											
3	Joint SwafS Citizen	12.05.2021	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Introducing the ROSiE		Oral presentation	

	Science Working Group							project to the joint Working Group			
4	Open Science Workshop 'Innovationen im Gesundheitswesen'	27.05.2021	Online event	Vienna	Austria	T. Konach	WP5	Member of the national RRI-platform	-	Oral presentation during the workshop session	Introducing the overall goals of ROSiE, and specifically tasks of the WP5
JUNE 2021											
5	The World Conferences on Research Integrity	29.05-02.06.2021	Online event	-	-	N. Foeger	WP5, WP8	Member of the Governing Board of the WCIR	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
6	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	09.06.2021	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Working Group communication and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Invitation to join ROSiE's Cross SwafS Stakeholder Forum
7	FAIR Festival	21-23.06.2021	Online event	-	-	T. Konach	WP5, WP8	Introducing the goals of ROSiE, and specifically of WP5	-	Participation in GO BUILD – GO TRAIN – GO CHANGE session	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project and to get in

											touch with the Implementation Teams of the GoFair Initiative
JULY 2021											
8	Digital Humanities Oxford Summer School 2021	12-15.07.2021	Online event	-	-	T. Konach	WP5, WP8	Introducing the ROSiE-project, the work in WP5 and possible links to the DH community		Oral presentation and a Q&A session	Introducing the goals of ROSiE, and specifically those of WP5; fostering synergies between the project and the DH community
AUGUST 2021											
9	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	11.08.2021	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Working Group communication and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Presented ROSiE's website and updates
SEPTEMBER 2021											
10	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	08.09.2021	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Working Group communication and exchange		Oral presentation	Presented and invited to join ROSiE's Stakeholder Board and Invitation to

								among CS SwafS			join ROSiE's Cross SwafS Stakeholder Forum
11	Open Science Fair	20-24.09.2021	Online event	-	-	T. Konach, N. Foeger	WP5	Presenting the WP5 within one of the conference's main topics: <i>Interdisciplinary collaborations: Networks, services, methods: Open science and data policies</i>		Poster presentation	Introducing the project to the international Open Science community and to the general public
12	Vienna Days of Academic Integrity/ Wiener Tage der Akademischen Integrität	22-25.09.2021	Tbc.	Vienna	Austria	N. Foeger/ T. Konach	WP8	Annual presentation of OeAWI at the Exhibition Area		Poster presentation	Introducing the project to the general public
13	ENRIO Conference	27-29.09.2021	Online event	-	-	N. Foeger/ T. Konach	WP8, WP5	Member of ENRIO	Presentation : Eight months digital	Workshop, oral presentations, sessions' chairing	Introducing the project and its newest developments

									whistleblowers platform: lessons learned Session chair: Research integrity training track	and panel discussions	
14	Open-Access-Days/ Open-Access-Tage	27-29.09.2021	Online event	Vienna	Austria	T. Konach	WP8, WP5	Ongoing cooperation with the organizer – the Open Science Network Austria		Poster presentation	Introducing the project to the national Open Science community and to the general public
15	Lectures, workshops and training activities	Ongoing	Virtual/in-person	-	Austria and abroad	N. Foeger	WP8	Lectures, workshops and training activities	-	-	Presentation of the project in each lecture, workshop or other training activity (permanent slide in each presentation)
16	ENRIO2021 Congress	27-29 September 2021	Online event	-	-	Olivier Le Gall (INRAE) Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA)	WP8	Olivier: Invited speaker	Olivier: Biodiversity, open science and research integrity	Olivier: Oral presentation	Olivier can/will briefly introduce ROSIE if no dedicated

						Etc.					talk is programmed
OCTOBER 2021											
17	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	13.10.2021	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Working Group communication and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Update on the didactic framework to develop training material for practicing responsible OS
18	American Society for Bioethics and Humanities	13-15 October 2021	Online event		USA	Søren Holm	General about ROSIE	Søren Holm: Speaker	Søren Holm: Does Open Science create an open season for new types of research misconduct?	Søren Holm: Oral presentation	Submitted, but not yet accepted (decision July 2021)
19	Conference organized by the Latvian National Commission for UNESCO	20-21 October 2021	Online event	-	Latvia	Signe Mezinska	WP7	Invited presentation on ethics in citizen science	Signe: Responsible citizen science in digital environment	Signe: Oral presentation	Information and program (in Latvian) https://www.unesco.lv/lv/jaunums/konference-spridis-par-etiskajiem-

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NOVEMBER 2021											
DECEMBER 2021											
20	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	08.12.20 21	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Mariana Vidal	WP4	Working Group communicati on and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Update on the project
2022											
No	Event	Dates	Venue	City	Country	Name of attendee/ Entity	Relate d ROSiE WP	Reason for participatio n	Title of contribution (if applicable)	Type of contribution (Oral presentation, Poster presentation)	Comments
JANUARY 2022											
21	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	12.01.20 22	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Francois Jost	WP4	Working Group communicati on and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Shared ROSiE's project updates
FEBRUARY 2022											

22	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	09.02.20 22	Online event	Berlin	Germany	Francois Jost	WP4	Working Group communicati on and exchange among CS SwafS		Oral presentation	Shared survey on experiences and challenges of practicing OS and news from ROSiE's 3 rd Cross SwafS stakeholder Forum for Responsible OS
MARCH 2022											
23	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	09.03.20 22	Online event	-	-	Beatriz Noriega	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project		Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
APRIL 2022											
24	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	13.04.20 22	Online event	-	-	Francois Jost	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project

MAY 2022											
25	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	11.05.2022	Online event	-	-	Beatriz Noriega	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
JUNE 2022											
26	Nordic-Baltic Network of Philosophy of Medicine, Annual Workshop	09.06.2022	Greifswald Wissenschaftscollege	Greifswald	Germany	Signe Mežinska/ University of Latvia	WP7	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	Citizen science in health and biomedical research: ethical issues and possible solutions	Oral presentation	
JULY 2022											
27	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	13.07.2022	Online event	-	-	Carole Chapin, Beatriz Noriega, Francois Jost	WP6, WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and obtaining feedback from participants on e.g, responsible OS, OS tools & related technology, and data	Technologies and Infrastructure in OS and CS at National and European Level	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project

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AUGUST 2022											
28	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	10.08.20 22	Online event	-	-	Francois Jost	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
SEPTEMBER 2022											
29	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	14.09.20 22	Online event	-	-	Beatriz Noriega	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
OCTOBER 2022											
30	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	12.10.20 22	Online event	-	-	Beatriz Noriega	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
31	ERCIM Ethics Working Group (Workshop)	17- 18/2022	Online event			Panagiotis Kavouras	WP8	Open Science: hopes, challenges and the intervention		Oral presentation	Opportunity to share the progress and the results achieved in project and discuss on the

								of ROSiE project'			new challenges and opportunities for research ethics in the field of Open Science.
NOVEMBER 2022											
32	Joint SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	09.11.2022	Online event	-	-	Francois Jost	WP4	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
33	22 nd FERCAP International Conference	Nov 27-30, 2022	Hybrid (ROSiE presented in person in K-Medi Hub: Daegu-Gyeongbuk Medical Innovation Foundation)	Daegu	South Korea	Rosemarie Bernabe Lisa Haberlein	WP5	Presenting the ROSiE policy document	Introducing the ROSiE Project & The ROSiE Policy Document on OS	Oral presentation in 1 full session	This was a well-attended event for RECs in Asia (around 400 participants in total). This is a very good way to gather the thoughts of participants from 3 rd countries but also to introduce the ROSiE project to them.

34	ETHNA System workshop for Transfer of Knowledge and Experience : First results from ETHNA System implementation process	24-25/11, 2022	Hybrid (ROSiE presented online)	Sofia	Bulgaria	Vana Stavridi	WP8	Implementation challenges of Open Science and the intervention of ROSiE project'	Presentation of ROSiE first outcomes	Oral presentation	An opportunity to work with other stakeholders and reflect on Gender equality, Open Science, Citizens' Engagement and Integrity Research (ethics) dimensions which should be taken into account in the implementation process of Ethical Governance of the Responsible Research and Innovation.
DECEMBER 2022											
No	Event	Dates	Venue	City	Country	Name of attendee/ Entity	Related ROSiE WP	Reason for participation	Title of contribution (if applicable)	Type of contribution (Oral presentation,	Comments

JANUARY 2023											
35	Workshop for piloting training materials	18 January 2023	National and Technical University of Athens	Athens	Greece	Panagiotis Kavouras, Eleni Spyraou, Vana Stavridi	WP8	-	Research Ethics and Research Integrity Issues in Open Science	Oral presentation	An opportunity to introduce the ROSiE project in our University and to discuss with other researchers on the research Ethics and Research Integrity issues in Open Science
36	EURODOC webinar on academic values	24 January, 2023	online	-	-	Tom Lindemann	WP3	Invited to kick-off a panel discussion on academic values	Academic values	Oral presentation + participation in panel discussion	
37	Annual BBMRI-ERIC ELSI expert meeting	January 25-26, 2023	BBMRI-ERIC	Vienna	Austria	Signe Mežinska/ University of Latvia	WP7	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE and providing updates on the project	Responsible Open Science in Biobanking	Oral presentation	

38	UiO Seminar on Integrity and International Collaborations in an Open Science Environment (co-sponsored by ROSiE)	January 27, 2023	University of Oslo	Oslo	Norway	Rosemarie Bernabe	WP9	Extending the reach of ROSiE to 3 rd countries	International collaborations and the European Governance of OS	Oral presentation	https://www.med.uio.no/helsam/english/research/centres/global-health/news-and-events/events/2023/integrity-and-international-collaborations-in-an-o.html
FEBRUARY 2023											
MARCH 2023											
39	University of Texas, Austin	March 9, 2023	Online Event	Austin, Texas	USA	Søren Holm	WP2	Enhancing the visibility of ROSiE in the USA	Research Integrity Challenges in Open Science Practices	Seminar	
40	EURODOC-ROSiE webinar	28 March, 2023	Online	-	-	Kadri Simm, Teodora Konach, Mathieu Rochambeau, Tom Lindemann	WP1, WP3, WP5	Invited by EURODOC to participate in their webinar series	tbd	1-hour online workshop	
APRIL 2023											

NOVEMBER 2023											
DECEMBER 2023											